

ISic1119

I.Sicily inscription 1119

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

sandstone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Panhormus

Place of origin (modern)

Palermo

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἰγνάτιος
2. Μαριανός
3. χρηστὸς
4. καὶ ἄμενῆτος
5. ἔζησεν ἔτη
6. · ν ·
7. ἡμέρας · ζ ·

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492733

EDR 140646

EDCS 39102275

PHI 140603

PHI 175750

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0299 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

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